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Food Security, Sustainable Agriculture and Forestry, Marine, Maritime and Inland Water Research and the Bioeconomy

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FuturEnzyme:

Technologies of the Future for Low-Cost Enzymes for Environment-Friendly Products

Final ID: 101000327

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FUTURENZYME PROJECT LEAFLET AND BROCHURE

D8.7

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Document information sheet

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Project brochures and leaflets

1. Introduction

This deliverable developed in month 12 describes the FuturEnzyme specific brochures, the workflow for obtaining them, their content, objectives and main messages, target audiences, and distribution channels.

In summary, brochures will be distributed to all project stakeholders, including consumers, the scientific community, and industries. They will explain the project objectives and achievements, describe the concrete undertaken actions and expected results to exploit the FuturEnzyme outputs, and communicate the potential societal, environmental and circular economy benefits of the FuturEnzyme research.

Four different brochures have been prepared to target the different needs and expectations of the various target groups of the FuturEnzyme project:

1. **FuturEnzyme, a project meeting costumers' demand.** This brochure is dedicated to consumers, analysing the trends and requests in the detergent, cosmetic and textile sectors and how the project is committed to meeting consumers' demand.
2. **FuturEnzyme project: who will benefit?** This brochure, dedicated to consumers, describes the positive impact of the FuturEnzyme project on consumers, companies, and the planet.
3. **Enzymes for sustainable everyday products: benefits and challenges.** This brochure is dedicated to academia as it provides more information on the potential benefits of using enzymes and insights on how the FuturEnzyme project is committed to overcoming the major challenges associated with discovering enzymes, with a focus on the bioprospecting platform.
4. **FuturEnzyme project: new consumer products for the green transition of European industries:** dedicated to industries, this last brochure analyses the main technological and environmental challenges associated with manufacturing consumer products and, thus, highlight how enzymes could improve the impact of these products, particularly how they can provide a bridge between circular economy and climate change mitigation.

Brochures incorporate the colours and figures of the already established project visual identity, including the project logo and original images and using the same colour palette. A strong visual identity makes the project recognisable at events, conferences, and online such as on social media, representing and differentiating FuturEnzyme initiatives at the international level.

Consorzio Italbiotec (ITB) is the appointed partner for elaborating, implementing, and distributing the brochures through FuturEnzyme communication channels. All project partners supported the revision of the content and will distribute the brochures among their communication channels.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Objectives**: this section describes the general and specific objectives of FuturEnzyme brochures and identifies the main target groups and the specific messages conveyed for each of them.
- **Content analysis**: this section describes and analyses in detail each brochure's content.
- **Workflow for preparing brochures**: this section describes how the brochures were prepared, revised, and finally validated by the three main project stakeholders to which the brochures are dedicated (consumers, industries, and academics).
- **Distribution channels**: this section analyses the main distribution channels of FuturEnzyme brochures and how we plan to disseminate them.

- **Outputs and results:** this section foresees the expected conversion rate to the project website and social media and how brochures will help increase project visibility among key target groups.

Brochures are displayed and can be easily downloaded from the FuturEnzyme website in the news section: <https://www.futureenzyme.eu/news/>. They are also accessible from the Home page of the project's website.

2. Objectives

General objectives

The general objectives of FuturEnzyme brochures are:

- To communicate the potential benefits of FuturEnzyme to multiple stakeholders;
- To increase project visibility at events and online;
- To provide concise information on project objectives and achievements;
- To exploit FuturEnzyme outputs and results.

Specific objectives

The specific objectives of FuturEnzyme brochures are related to the target audience.

1. **Consumers and general society:** consumers, as directly users of daily-used products and demanders of eco-friendly, efficient and durable products, whose needs and requests can affect production choice at industrial level, are the main target of FuturEnzyme brochures (two out of four are dedicated to this group). The specific objectives for this target group are:
 - To raise awareness of the environmental impact of consumer products of daily use and the role that consumers may have in fighting climate change;
 - To promote sustainable consumption behaviours to significantly decrease environmental impacts;
 - To improve the general knowledge of enzymes and their potential benefits on consumers, companies and the planet.
2. **Companies:** supporting a green shift in the production models of main consumer products, FuturEnzyme brochures clearly address companies as one of the main project target groups. The specific objectives for this target group are:
 - To industrially exploit project outputs and results;
 - To encourage the technological transfer to other users and manufacturers;
 - To promote sustainable production models and support the improvement of environmental responsibility in the industry;
 - To offer industry enzymatic solutions for improving existing consumer products on the market, or designing new ones to mitigate climate change and implement a circular economy model;
 - To make new enzyme-based products more accessible to consumers;
 - To encourage the industrial dialogue about FuturEnzyme topics.
3. **Scientific community:** finally, project brochures involve the scientific community with the following specific objectives:
 - To stimulate the active participation of the scientific community;
 - To encourage future research on eco-friendly enzyme-based products;
 - To accelerate the process of identifying enzymes responding to the industry and public's demands.

3. Content analysis

All project brochures are composed of 6 pages.

The first page includes the project logo, project acronym and full name, the EU flag and the disclaimer on project funding: "Project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No [101000327]".

The last page includes all partners' logos, links, and QR code to the project website (**Figure 1**). This page also repeats the FuturEnzyme logo and the EU flag as well as the disclaimer previously described.

Figure 1. QR code to project website included in the last page of all project brochures

All brochures also include the FuturEnzyme original images and its colour palette as described in Deliverable 8.3.

Brochure 1 - FuturEnzyme, a project meeting customers' demand

This brochure, dedicated to consumers, describes how the project is committed to meeting consumers' demands. After analysing the trends and requests in the detergent, cosmetic and textile sectors, this brochure acknowledges the fact that, because of their extensive use, the environmental impact of this type of products should be reduced, aiming to raise awareness of the environmental impact on consumer products and the role that consumers have in fighting climate change.

Brochure No 1 also describes which measures manufacturer partners have implemented to make their processes and products more sustainable. After that, the brochure gives insight into project activity that will develop sustainable consumer products that align with consumers' needs and requests.

Brochure 2 - FuturEnzyme project: who will benefit?

This brochure, dedicated to consumers, aims at improving the general knowledge of how we can benefit from enzymes. Indeed, the FuturEnzyme project aims to develop at least nine enzymes to be implemented in real consumer products, making them more environmentally friendly, valuable, functional and sustainable. This will benefit consumers and companies by developing new ecological products with new effective properties, and the planet by reducing the environmental impact of consumer' products. The brochure finally analyses how the project will achieve these benefits in its three main target areas: detergents, cosmetics and textiles.

Brochure 3 - Enzymes for sustainable everyday products: benefits and challenges

This brochure, dedicated to the scientific community, provides more information on the potential benefits of using enzymes and insights on how FuturEnzyme project is committed to overcoming the major challenges associated with discovering enzymes, focusing on the bioprospecting platform. By describing enzymes' potential benefits and pivotal assets in industrial processes and consumer products, this brochure aims to encourage research on eco-friendly enzyme-based products. However, the brochures also highlight the main bottlenecks that hinder enzyme-based consumer products' economic competitiveness and environmental sustainability. Moreover, it describes how the FuturEnzyme project, with its innovative machine-learning-based platform, is committed to overcoming these major challenges, accelerating the process of enzyme discovery.

Brochure 4 - FuturEnzyme project: new consumer products for the green transition of European industries

This last brochure is dedicated to companies mainly operating in the three target areas of the project (detergents, textiles, cosmetics). However, all industries that produce consumer products and are interested in making their products and processes greener could find interesting information in this brochure.

Starting with describing the challenges of detergent, cosmetic ingredients and textile production and bio-processing, this document also analyses the increased interest of EU consumers in environmentally friendly products, a trend that is driving the green transition in many industries. FuturEnzyme, thus, provides a solution to develop sustainable consumer products that are aligned with market trends and circular economy.

4. Workflow for preparing brochures

The workflow followed for preparing the final version of the brochures included ITB as the lead beneficiary of this activity, CSIC as the project coordinator and all partners for revision and validation of brochures content. The workflow included the following steps (**Figure 2**):

Figure 2. Workflow for preparing brochures

1. **Content definition.** After identifying the main project target groups (consumers, company, scientific community) and analysing the most effective tone for each stakeholder, specific content for each brochure was defined in a first draft with ITB, which was revised and implemented with the help of the project coordinator, CSIC.
2. **Collection of inputs from all partners and content revision.** The first draft of the four brochures was circulated among partners to collect their input. After merging all received inputs, the final drafts of the brochures were shared again with all project partners for a final content revision.
3. **Brochures' layout.** ITB's graphic designer incorporates both the original images of the FuturEnzyme project and its colour palette into the brochures' layout to reinforce the project's visual identity. The text draft approved by all project partners was typeset in an A5 slide format. Rather than preparing short brochures (under 4 pages) full of text content, we have preferred to have longer documents with larger font sizes and more images and colours to make the brochures more effective.
4. **Brochures' validation by project stakeholders.** Finally, we tested the tone and content of each brochure with the respective target groups to make sure that they would have the necessary impact. ITB organised short focus groups with consumers to collect feedback on the project communication materials relevant to consumers in relation to the consumers' target group. Feedback was collected among the academic and industrial project partners about brochures related to industry and academia. Feedback from stakeholders in this validation step was useful to further implement each brochure's content.
5. **Translation of project brochures:** project brochures dedicated to consumers (Brochure No1 and No2) were translated in Italian, Spanish and German (main partners' languages) to widen the impact on the society by making the message easier to understand.

5. Distribution channels

The main distribution channel for brochures dissemination is **social media**. The A5-slide format of brochures is suitable for sharing the brochures on social media both as downloadable materials and as single specific posts. So far, ITB planned the following dissemination timetable of brochures on project social media (both LinkedIn and Twitter):

28 th April 2022	Publication of the link to download all project brochures
06 th May 2022	Post dedicated to brochure No. 1 for consumers
20 th May 2022	Post dedicated to brochure No. 2 for consumers
03 rd June 2022	Post dedicated to brochure No. 3 for academia and the scientific community
17 th June 2022	Post dedicated to brochure No. 4 for industries

Other distribution channels for FuturEnzyme brochures are:

- **Project website:** all brochures are available for download from the news section (<https://www.futureenzyme.eu/news/>). Each brochure also has its dedicated link for visualisation and download:
Brochure No. 1: <https://www.futureenzyme.eu/news/#pdf-brochure-1-4-0/1/>
Brochure No. 2: <https://www.futureenzyme.eu/news/#pdf-brochure-2-4-0/1/>
Brochure No. 3: <https://www.futureenzyme.eu/news/#pdf-brochure-3-3-0/1/>
Brochure No. 4: <https://www.futureenzyme.eu/news/#pdf-brochure-4-4-0/1/>
They are also accessible from the Home page.
- **Newsletter:** the first project newsletter that will be issued in June will contain one news on FuturEnzyme brochures with the link for download.
- **Emails to partners, AB members, and their collaborators:** brochures (online material) will be distributed by email to all partner's collaborators, including stakeholders, AB members, academic groups, other consortia, secondary schools, and universities with which we collaborate or organise activities, to transfer offices from the different partners, to responsible of Environmental Ministry, etc. This will be done at local, regional, national, European and worldwide levels.
- **Project events and external fairs and conferences:** 200 copies (50 for each brochure) will be printed and distributed to project partners during Madrid's first annual project meeting to show how brochures should be printed and the final result. Brochures will be printed as a short booklet in A5 format, like the image provided in **Figure 3**. Printed brochures will also be distributed during future project events and external fairs and conferences.

Figure 3. Brochures' format

6. Final project brochures

FuturEnzyme project brochures in the slide format (as shared on social media and other online communications channels) and in the A5 format (used for printing) are attached to this deliverable.

FuturEnzyme. Technologies of the FUTURE for low-cost ENZYMEs for environment-friendly products

Project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020.
Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No [101000327]

FuturEnzyme, a project meeting customers' demands

Visions for the consumer products of 2030

There is a worldwide concern for the **protection of the environment** that clearly implies daily used goods such as **detergents, textiles and cosmetics**. The average current consumption in a European household with 4 members in a year is:

**16-20 kg
of detergent**

**30 kg
of textiles**

**1 kg
of cosmetics**

By 2030 this consumption will grow at an annual rate of 4.8-6.3%. Because of their extensive use, the environmental impact from production to consumption should be as low as possible, reducing water pollution and consumption, chemical usage, waste production and energy consumption, increased biodegradability and maximum efficiency.

The number of manufacturers that give an important consideration to the environment is constantly increasing. For decades this matter has been a priority to some of them, such as our manufacturer partners, Henkel, Schoeller and Evonik; they have been continuously working to bring more efficient, greener products to consumers. In numbers:

Henkel has reduced in the last 11 years per ton of product

- 44% CO₂ emissions
- 44 % of waste
- 28 % of water

Evonik has lowered

- 44 % CO₂ emissions within the last 13 years
- 5% waste within the last 3 years

Schoeller

Produces under bluesign® system guidelines since 2001

Has reduced to half the energy they use for warm water by applying heat recovery; moreover, approx. 30% of their own electricity consumption is currently produced by the photovoltaic system (solar power), installed in 2019

Generates wastewater that can be fed into the normal wastewater

Uses schoeller®-ecody which saves around 1 ton of CO₂ emissions and additional water for the dyeing of 2 tons of textiles.

All these efforts already make a difference, but our determination is to keep **pursuing a 100% sustainable model** of production and consumption through constant innovation. Furthermore, several policy initiatives have already been undertaken at the political level to make the **European Union the first climate-neutral region**.

*Enzymes give our products a higher environmental excellence:
FuturEnzyme's ambition to meet customers' demand*

Constant innovation is required to meet the high standards required by consumers and industries. One such innovation is the use of **enzymes** (proteins that accelerate chemical reactions), substituting the use of chemical agents while reducing energy and water consumption. FuturEnzyme aims to approach the complex reality and challenges of detergent, cosmetic ingredients and textile production through the development of microbial enzymes with enhanced performances compared to the existing ones in the market.

For instance:

Adding few grams of enzymes to a liter of detergent allows using “cold-water”, which saves 30% of energy during the wash cycle, while increasing stain removal; moreover, our enzymes will be stable to withstand different washing programmes and storage conditions

Producing a textile from yarn requires multiple steps that use chemicals (1.5-3.0% by weight) and need to be eliminated with an extensive amount of water; that can be significantly reduced by using enzymes to remove such chemicals. Furthermore, our enzymes will remove different types of substances such as oils from different types of fabrics without damaging their surface

Along the production of cosmetic ingredients, such as hyaluronic acid, high temperatures are needed. Their bio-processing with enzymes will lower the temperature and thus energy consumption. What is more, our enzymes will cut molecules such as hyaluronic acid to pieces of a defined size with best anti-ageing properties

In addition, the cost of enzymes must be low enough to make their use economically viable.

FuturEnzyme will allow selecting “intelligent” enzymes that meet the characteristics of efficiency and stability required by industry through a massive search of enzymes from microorganisms and their massive analysis using supercomputers. Biotechnology techniques will be applied to improve, technically and economically, their performance and productivity.

We strongly believe that with these enzymes, that themselves are eco-ingredients, **consumers will have at their disposal more environmentally friendly, effective and innovative liquid detergents, anti-ageing cosmetics and textiles.**

Partners

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delle Ricerche

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www.futureenzyme.eu

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FuturEnzyme project

The FuturEnzyme consortium is organised with a clear objective: to establish and combine a series of technologies (including digital ones) to develop **enzymes at low cost** and with **exquisite performance and stability**.

FuturEnzyme project has the ambition to develop at least nine enzymes to be implemented **in real consumer products**, particularly liquid detergents, textiles and anti-ageing ingredients for cosmetics, making them more **environmentally friendly, valuable, functional and sustainable**.

Who will benefit?

WHO WILL BENEFIT?

Consumers, because they will have products that have been processed according to ecological principles and with better and/or new properties (e.g. better washability, **better anti-ageing properties**, greener fabrics, etc.)

Who will benefit?

WHO WILL BENEFIT?

Companies, as having greener innovative products will allow opening up **new markets and gain better visibility**

The planet, as greenhouse gas impacts, water and energy consumption, and chemical releases will be substantially reduced, thus contributing at least to **climate change mitigation, pollution prevention, protection and recovery of biodiversity and ecosystems and circular economy.**

Cosmetic sector:

by focusing on hyaluronic acid, a very large natural polymer that has limited biological anti-ageing activity because of its big size and low penetration into the skin. Cleaving the large anti-ageing ingredient is essential to improve its activity but the existing technologies like thermal degradation are unsuitable, forming very short fragments that are not appropriate

as cosmetic ingredients. The project's ambition is, therefore, to develop enzymes which allow to generate **hyaluronic acid fragments with a desired size in a production process running at low temperatures and show a more effective anti-ageing activity**

Textile sector:

by integrating efficient enzymes in the manufacturing steps of textiles and ensuring a more environmental friendly process from yarn to garments and to develop **smart textiles which have additional benefits for consumers**.

In these steps many chemicals are employed, that need to be eliminated at the end of each of the processing steps. Thus enzymes take over the role of chemicals resulting in a positive environmental impact.

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Enzymes for sustainable everyday products: benefits and challenges

In a world facing major environmental threats, **enzymes, as green catalysts**, can help alleviate global-warming problems and create consumer products that are more respectful for the environment. The pivotal assets provided by enzymes in industrial processes and consumer products include:

**Lower
energy
footprint**

**Reduced
waste
production
and chemicals'
consumption**

**Safer
process
conditions**

**The
use of
renewable
feedstocks**

However, several bottlenecks hinder the economic competitiveness and environmental sustainability of enzyme-based consumer products:

Limited repertoire of available enzymes with the characteristics suitable for use in everyday consumer products.

The inability to bio-prospect enzymes fitting manufacturers' specifications. Indeed, finding and producing a single novel enzyme requires multiple **costly** (approx. 30,000 €) **and time-consuming** (approx. 15 months) iterative cycles.

The limited incorporation of artificial intelligence for enzyme discovery. As example, a wealth of more than 280 million sequences (each representing an enzyme) are available in public databases and new sequences can be obtained at low price, but little use has been made of it so far because the absence of advanced computational resources (hardware, software) to screen them.

Enzymes often need **gradual improvements**. However, **most current engineering efforts applied to known enzymes come up short to meet industrial needs**, and concerns remain about using current machine learning algorithms to improve new enzymes.

Poor enzyme productivity along with high development, production, and formulation costs once an enzyme is selected and further implemented.

All together, the major challenge and biggest hurdle when approaching the bio-processing of consumer products with enzymes is to develop the new enzymes in timescales short enough to meet the needs of consumers and the climate and circular bioeconomy objectives.

FuturEnzyme project

FuturEnzyme's ambition is to develop **"intelligent" enzymes** that meet the characteristics of efficiency and stability required by industry. This will be achieved through a massive bio-prospecting of enzymes from microorganisms, including those from remote and inaccessible places, and their massive analysis with the

help of supercomputers. On the other hand, a number of techniques will be applied to improve, both technically and economically, the performance and productivity of the best enzymes. We strongly believe that with these enzymes, that themselves are **eco-ingredients**, we will guarantee not only **high ecological standards** (reduction of water pollution and consumption, chemical usage, waste production and energy consumption) but also **high performance** of three consumer products (cosmetics, textiles and detergents) already in the market.

Expected results: experimentation and digitalization for enzymes bio-prospecting

FuturEnzyme project has the ambition to develop **2 web-based resources** to screen for enzymes meeting the manufacturers' specifications required by detergent, textile and cosmetic sectors:

- **An online semi-automatic Hidden Markov Model based search tool**
- **An online machine learning-based predictive search tool**

The development of these tools will be based on two main points. First, detailed **knowledge of the characteristics** that enzymes must meet for inclusion in liquid detergents and the bio-processing of anti-ageing cosmetic ingredients and textiles. Second, the detailed analysis of a large number of enzymes to help us **associate sequences with properties** desired by industry. The FuturEnzyme high-tech platform will be also based on different technologies, including:

- **Activity-based enzyme bio-prospecting**
- **Cultivation of novel microbes**
- **Disruptive enzyme engineering approaches**
- **Enzyme implementation through immobilisation and shielding technology**

- **Beyond state-of-the-art multiple expression technologies in bacteria, yeast, fungi and archaea**
- **Biocatalysis**

Starting from 1,000 enzymes pre-selected by using computer- and functional-based screens, the project will select 180 enzymes with validated manufacturer requirements, of which 18 will be engineered to obtain a 100-fold more effectiveness compared to the existing ones in the market. **At the end, 9 enzymes** with verified features will be developed to improve 3 consumer products (cosmetics, textiles and detergents) already in the market.

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**FuturEnzyme. Technologies of
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Challenges of detergent, cosmetic ingredients and textile production and bio-processing

Detergents:

Large annual energy and water consumption during the washing process

The entire volume of detergent used in a washing cycle is released to the waste water stream

Concerns about the detergents' actual washing capacity at low temperature

Concerns about the storage stability of enzymes in liquid detergents in emerging markets.

Textiles:

The manufacturing process requires massive amounts of water, heating energy and chemicals

Consumers expect high quality textiles, being equally colored and having sophisticated benefits, like absorbing moisture, being resistant to mechanical stress, avoiding sweating and thus the textile industry is constantly looking for meeting these consumers' needs.

Cosmetics:

Producing eco-friendly cosmetic ingredients remains a challenge, as their processing commonly requires the use of chemicals and high temperature

Consumers increasingly demand cosmetics with better properties, e.g. maintaining skin looking young and avoiding-ageing.

European consumers would like to access to more environmentally friendly products

Consumers are becoming increasingly aware of the negative impact of everyday products on the environment and are searching for alternatives that could be beneficial for the planet.

Socio-economic evaluations that assess consumer perception of the environmental impact of daily life habits revealed that approximately **90% of consumers have a more positive image of a company that supports biotechnology and pursue sustainable values.** Furthermore, about **50% of Europeans** are willing to pay a **green tax for a more sustainable alternative.**

FuturEnzyme project: New consumer products for the green transition of European industries

FuturEnzyme's ambition is to approach the complex reality and obvious challenges of detergent, anti-ageing cosmetic ingredients and textile production and bio-processing through the development of microbial enzymes with enhanced performances compared to the existing ones in the market.

For that, FuturEnzyme's goal is to develop **"intelligent" enzymes** that meet the characteristics of efficiency and stability required by industry. This will be achieved through a massive bio-prospecting of enzymes from microorganisms, including those from remote and inaccessible places, and their massive analysis with the help of supercomputers.

On the other hand, several techniques will be applied to improve, both technically and economically, the performance and productivity of the best enzymes.

We strongly believe that with these enzymes, that themselves are **eco-ingredients**, we will guarantee not only **high ecological standards** (reduction of water pollution and consumption, chemical usage, waste production and energy consumption)

but also **high performance** of three consumer products already in the market:

A **laundry detergent**, with enzymes being stable under different storage conditions, with reduced chemical quantity in the formulation and effective at lower washing temperature reducing the energy consumption of a washing cycle

A **hyaluronic acid-based cosmetic cream**, starting with an enzymatic processes to produce, at low temperature and aqueous solution, eco-hyaluronic acid with better defined molecular weight that is expected to have better anti-ageing properties

A **textile** that is produced with more sustainable (less water and energy consumption) enzyme-based pre-treatment and finishing steps, and improved fabric properties.

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By 2030 this consumption will grow at an annual rate of 4.8-6.3%. Because of their extensive use, the environmental impact from production to consumption should be as low as possible, reducing water pollution and consumption, chemical usage, waste production and energy consumption, increased biodegradability and maximum efficiency.

The number of manufacturers that give an important consideration to the environment is constantly increasing. For decades this matter has been a priority to some of them, such as our manufacturer partners, Henkel, Schoeller and Evonik; they have been continuously working to bring more efficient, greener products to consumers. In numbers:

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FuturEnzyme project

The FuturEnzyme consortium is organised with a clear objective: to establish and combine a series of technologies (including digital ones) to develop **enzymes at low cost** and with **exquisite performance and stability**.

FuturEnzyme project has the ambition to develop at least nine enzymes to be implemented **in real consumer products**, particularly liquid detergents, textiles and anti-ageing ingredients for cosmetics, making them more **environmentally friendly, valuable, functional and sustainable**.

Who will benefit?

WHO WILL BENEFIT?

Consumers, because they will have products that have been processed according to ecological principles and with better and/or new properties (e.g. better washability, **better anti-ageing properties**, greener fabrics, etc.)

Who will benefit?

WHO WILL BENEFIT?

Companies, as having greener innovative products will allow opening up **new markets and gain better visibility**

The planet, as greenhouse gas impacts, water and energy consumption, and chemical releases will be substantially reduced, thus contributing at least to **climate change mitigation, pollution prevention, protection and recovery of biodiversity and ecosystems and circular economy.**

Expected impacts of FuturEnzyme for consumers and the environment

The tools, enzymes, and products to be implemented in FuturEnzyme will help increase the number of eco-conscious consumers, currently accounting for about 50% of the Europeans.

How will FuturEnzyme achieve benefits?

HOW WILL FUTURENZYME ACHIEVE BENEFITS?

Detergent sector:

by integrating more efficient and stable enzymes with a double aim. First, to **decrease the amount of chemicals** used in detergents, which are released into the environment after the washing cycle. Second, increasing the percentage of **low washing temperature** (20-40°C) can almost halve the energy consumption of a standard washing cycle. To reach this goal, our industrial partner requested enzymes active against stubborn stains and stable under washing and storage conditions

Cosmetic sector:

by focusing on hyaluronic acid, a very large natural polymer that has limited biological anti-ageing activity because of its big size and low penetration into the skin. Cleaving the large anti-ageing ingredient is essential to improve its activity but the existing technologies like thermal degradation are unsuitable, forming very short fragments that are not appropriate as cosmetic ingredients. The project's ambition is, therefore, to develop enzymes which allow to generate **hyaluronic acid fragments with a desired size in a production process running at low temperatures and show a more effective anti-ageing activity**

Textile sector:

by integrating efficient enzymes in the manufacturing steps of textiles and ensuring a more environmental friendly process from yarn to garments and to develop **smart textiles which have additional benefits for consumers.**

In these steps many chemicals are employed, that need to be eliminated at the end of each of the processing steps. Thus enzymes take over the role of chemicals resulting in a positive environmental impact.

Partners

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www.futureenzyme.eu

FuturEnzyme. Technologies of
the FUTURE for low-cost ENZYMEs
for environment-friendly products

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Enzymes for sustainable everyday products: benefits and challenges

In a world facing major environmental threats, **enzymes, as green catalysts**, can help alleviate global-warming problems and create consumer products that are more respectful for the environment. The pivotal assets provided by enzymes in industrial processes and consumer products include:

However, several bottlenecks hinder the economic competitiveness and environmental sustainability of enzyme-based consumer products:

Limited repertoire of available enzymes with the characteristics suitable for use in everyday consumer products.

The inability to bio-prospect enzymes fitting manufacturers' specifications. Indeed, finding and producing a single novel enzyme requires multiple **costly** (approx. 30,000 €) **and time-consuming** (approx. 15 months) iterative cycles.

The limited incorporation of artificial intelligence for enzyme discovery. As example, a wealth of more than 280 million sequences (each representing an enzyme) are available in public databases and new sequences can be obtained at low price, but little use has been made of it so far because the absence of advanced computational resources (hardware, software) to screen them.

Enzymes often need **gradual improvements**. However, **most current engineering efforts applied to known enzymes come up short to meet industrial needs**, and concerns remain about using current machine learning algorithms to improve new enzymes.

Poor enzyme productivity along with high development, production, and formulation costs once an enzyme is selected and further implemented.

All together, the major challenge and biggest hurdle when approaching the bio-processing of consumer products with enzymes is to develop the new enzymes in timescales short enough to meet the needs of consumers and the climate and circular bio-economy objectives.

FuturEnzyme project

FuturEnzyme's ambition is to develop **"intelligent" enzymes** that meet the characteristics of efficiency and stability required by industry. This will be achieved through a massive bio-prospecting of enzymes from microorganisms, including those from remote and inaccessible places, and their massive analysis with the help of supercomputers. On the other hand, a number of techniques will be applied to improve, both technically and economically, the performance and productivity of the best enzymes. We strongly believe that with these enzymes, that themselves are **eco-ingredients**, we will guarantee not only **high ecological standards** (reduction of water pollution and consumption, chemical usage, waste production and energy consumption) but also **high performance** of three consumer products (cosmetics, textiles and detergents) already in the market.

Expected results: experimentation and digitalization for enzymes bio-prospecting

FuturEnzyme project has the ambition to develop **2 web-based resources** to screen for enzymes meeting the manufacturers' specifications required by detergent, textile and cosmetic sectors:

- **An online semi-automatic Hidden Markov Model based search tool**
- **An online machine learning-based predictive search tool**

The development of these tools will be based on two main points. First, detailed **knowledge of the characteristics** that enzymes must meet for inclusion in liquid detergents and the bio-processing of anti-ageing cosmetic ingredients and textiles. Second, the detailed analysis of a large number of enzymes to help us **associate sequences with properties** desired by industry. The FuturEnzyme high-tech platform will be also based on different technologies, including:

- **Activity-based enzyme bio-prospecting**
- **Cultivation of novel microbes**
- **Disruptive enzyme engineering approaches**
- **Enzyme implementation through immobilisation and shielding technology**
- **Beyond state-of-the-art multiple expression technologies in bacteria, yeast, fungi and archaea**
- **Biocatalysis**

Starting from 1,000 enzymes pre-selected by using computer- and functional-based screens, the project will select 180 enzymes with validated manufacturer requirements, of which 18 will be engineered to obtain a 100-fold more effectiveness compared to the existing ones in the market. **At the end, 9 enzymes** with verified features will be developed to improve 3 consumer products (cosmetics, textiles and detergents) already in the market.

Partners

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Challenges of detergent, cosmetic ingredients and textile production and bio-processing

Detergents:

Large annual energy and water consumption during the washing process

The entire volume of detergent used in a washing cycle is released to the waste water stream

Concerns about the detergents' actual washing capacity at low temperature

Concerns about the storage stability of enzymes in liquid detergents in emerging markets.

Textiles:

The manufacturing process requires massive amounts of water, heating energy and chemicals

Consumers expect high quality textiles, being equally colored and having sophisticated benefits, like absorbing moisture, being resistant to mechanical stress, avoiding sweating and thus the textile industry is constantly looking for meeting these consumers' needs.

Cosmetics:

Producing eco-friendly cosmetic ingredients remains a challenge, as their processing commonly requires the use of chemicals and high temperature

Consumers increasingly demand cosmetics with better properties, e.g. maintaining skin looking young and avoiding ageing.

European consumers would like to access to more environmentally friendly products

Consumers are becoming increasingly aware of the negative impact of everyday products on the environment and are searching for alternatives that could be beneficial for the planet.

Socio-economic evaluations that assess consumer perception of the environmental impact of daily life habits revealed that approximately **90% of consumers have a more positive image of a company that supports biotechnology and pursue sustainable values.** Furthermore, about **50% of Europeans** are willing to pay a **green tax for a more sustainable alternative.**

FuturEnzyme project: New consumer products for the green transition of European industries

FuturEnzyme's ambition is to approach the complex reality and obvious challenges of detergent, anti-ageing cosmetic ingredients and textile production and bio-processing through the development of microbial enzymes with enhanced performances compared to the existing ones in the market.

For that, FuturEnzyme's goal is to develop **"intelligent" enzymes** that meet the characteristics of efficiency and stability required by industry. This will be achieved through a massive bio-prospecting of enzymes from microorganisms, including those from remote and inaccessible places, and their massive analysis with the help of supercomputers.

On the other hand, several techniques will be applied to improve, both technically and economically, the performance and productivity of the best enzymes.

We strongly believe that with these enzymes, that themselves are **eco-ingredients**, we will guarantee not only **high ecological standards** (reduction of water pollution and consumption, chemical usage, waste production and energy consumption)

but also **high performance** of three consumer products already in the market:

A **laundry detergent**, with enzymes being stable under different storage conditions, with reduced chemical quantity in the formulation and effective at lower washing temperature reducing the energy consumption of a washing cycle

A **hyaluronic acid-based cosmetic cream**, starting with an enzymatic processes to produce, at low temperature and aqueous solution, eco-hyaluronic acid with better defined molecular weight that is expected to have better anti-ageing properties

A **textile** that is produced with more sustainable (less water and energy consumption) enzyme-based pre-treatment and finishing steps, and improved fabric properties.

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